

MANIFESTATION OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN ADOLESCENCE

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the issues of destructive religious, cultural, extremist and terrorist flows that negatively affect the stability, spiritual rise of the Republic of Uzbekistan, theoretical-practical analysis of the activities of groups, describing, classifying the Genesis, essence and content of the concepts of a destructive group, relying on existing scientific theories, creating a certain socio-psychological basis for the Particular importance is given to aspects specific to adolescence in the formation of destructive behavior. Issues of the manifestation of socio-psychological characteristics in adolescence have been studied.*

Keywords: *adolescent age, crisis, education, upbringing, destructive, imagination, social, spiritual-educational, inner world, spiritual state, moral-ethical qualities—discipline, responsiveness, kindness, sincerity, truthfulness, humanity, humility, expansionism, reluctance, contentedness, hard work.*

The upbringing of competent, purposeful and bright young people with modern knowledge and skills, who can take responsibility for the worthy future of the country is one of the most important tasks of today. In the current process of globalization, avoiding attacks aimed at acquiring the consciousness of the individual, forming a strong spirituality in the minds of everyone, protecting young people from the influence of destructive groups, ideological immunity in the minds of every citizen in our society, relying on our national and spiritual values, content of antimanipulative, assertive behavior in ensuring security is one of

In our country, great work is being carried out to strengthen the intellectual and creative potential of young people, to increase their immunity to the reforms carried out in our country. "For us," the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan said M.Mirziyoev, - another issue that will never lose its relevance and significance, is the task of raising our children as independent - minded people, possessing modern knowledge and professions, with a strong life position, truly patriotic people. It is not a secret for anyone that the issue of youth education is becoming more important, especially in a now complex period when evil dangers such as religious extremism, terrorism, drugs, human trafficking, illegal migration, "mass culture" wreak havoc on the head of humanity" [103], in our country, special attention is paid to the issue of youth education.

This is one of the factors that serve as collateral in ensuring the safety of the individual in the future, as well as the security of the community and the state.

It is known that the head of state had put forward 5 important initiatives to establish work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres on the basis of a new system.

Destructive religious, cultural, extremist and terrorist currents, which adversely affect the stability of the Republic of Uzbekistan, or rather its social, spiritual rise, theoretical-practical analysis of the activities of groups, describing the Genesis, essence and content of the concepts of a destructive group, Idea, relying on existing scientific theories, classification, creating a certain socio-psychological basis for the, pedagogy and all social and humanitarian Sciences in general

are among the most important tasks faced. It is advisable to pay attention to adolescence so that young people do not fall under the influence of these ideas.

Age periods are known from the sciences of Psychology, by the time of adolescence, the child's organism grows rapidly and disproportionately. This increase can sometimes cause the child to feel worse and cause certain physiological disorders to come. All these cases concern the child and lead to his nervousness. Feeling that he is getting older and changing, the teenager now begins to develop a need to live with adult fantasies. The teenager begins to pretend to be full as an adult, to show that he has grown up .

Adolescents become interested in some negative behaviors during this period, including smoking and alcoholism. A teenager who does not feel normally well in a new role, like an adult smoker, drinker, is very deeply worried, and a state of crisis (crisis) arises from him. Also, the spiritual growth of this crisis teenager is associated with changes in the psyche. During this period, the social status of the child changes new attitudes arise with his loved ones, friends, peers. But, the biggest change comes in the circumstances of his inner world, rukhiy. Most cases of self-dissatisfaction in a teenager are observed. The fact that existing fictions in itself do not coincide with the changes that are happening in it today causes the teenager to become nervous, worrying about the second side. This can create negative thoughts and fears in the child himself. Some adolescents are concerned about why those around them cannot realize that adults are often confronting their parents. This condition also causes them to feel nervous inside themselves. The most basic tasks of adults during this period are to help the adolescent to correctly understand his problem and live freely, correctly.

In human ontogenesis, puberty ranges from 10-11 to 14-15 years. In most students, the transition to adolescence mainly begins in the 5th grade. "Now he is not a child—he, still not a big one," - sudden changes in physiological development begin to occur. These changes are physiological, as well as psychological changes. Physiological change is the beginning of sexual maturity and, in connection with this, the perfect development and growth of all organs in the body, the beginning of the reshaping of the structures of the cell and organism. In his time, L.S. Vigotsky called such a state of affairs a "crisis in psychic development". After a small school period, the child experiences mainly two stages in the process of forming his self-attitude as a separately acquired person. [122],

How many are the tasks that are currently required to be carried out when conducting educational work for adolescents of this age. Another relevant aspect of the issue is that the personality of young people constitutes one of the main subjects of security. They make it possible to determine what social, economic, political, informational, psychological, cultural, ideological influences need to be studied in socio-psychological terms of the security of their person. In turn, these serve to significantly enrich the program activities planned within the framework of the state youth policy adopted in our country.

Today, a number of destructive groups operate in the territories of countries around the world, causing several problems in the political, socio-cultural, educational life of these states. Unfortunately, even in our country, some groups seek to attract young people to their influence in different ways, seriously threatening the security of society and the state in the religious, cultural, spiritual, social and political sphere.

The implementation of the upbringing of the perfect generation is one of the important strategic issues, and taking into account the demographic characteristics of our country, it is

considered from tasks of not only theoretical, but also practical importance. At a time when today's globalization processes are taking place, the struggle for the human mind and soul is going on sharply with the help of various methods and Means. These actions are aimed directly at young people, and are aimed at forming negative attitudes towards our national traditions and values, towards the policies that are being carried out in our country. This is done by forming ideas, giving directions that are needed with the help of certain media, public art and culture.

The result can also be observed in cases of expansion, manifested in the religious, cultural, social, spiritual spheres of society. Those cases that in turn have a tragic character are likely to have the following consequences:

- narrowing of the circle of youth social contacts;
- change in the content of values;
- young people live only for today, and the prospect unthinkable;
- from places other than the family, work, training team striving to find.

The personality of the hulking the formation of visions will continue to change and develop throughout his life. But the main facets of the image of the Hulk make them with the active participation of family members, as a result of the influence of the surrounding factors and the attitude of the individual to the factors, new sensations of behavior begin to appear. In this respect, there are hulking sensations associated with the interests of the social system of the same period of people who lived in each historical period. Usually each individual's hulking character and their associated imagination are very different, which are inextricably linked to his volitional and moral qualities. These sensations include willpower, independence, determination, endurance, perseverance, self-control. The moral and ethical qualities of behavior are discipline, responsiveness, kindness, sincerity, truthfulness, humanity, humility, broadness, reluctance, concordance, hard work.

The appearance and formation of a certain hulking sensation in a person is reflected in the adaptation (orientation) to a certain value, giving them an approximate assessment. It can only be said that the subject is directed towards value when he projects a certain emotion in his mind. The formation of orientation in relation to value is activated by the need as well as adaptation to activity. Attention is paid to the behavior of the contemplative people about spirituality. Because of this, the essence of spirituality is fully reflected in behavior.

In the same sense, the hulking imagery is highly formed social imagery.

The "hulking imagination" is contained in the general imagination of the individual. Imagination is a system of phenomena related to the person's knowledge of the surrounding being, his personal experience. This or that object or phenomenon the absence of knowledge signals the absence of imagination. Hulkur is a concept that combines images with the concept of "spirituality" and embodies the inner spiritual experiences, mental abilities, perception of society, nation, as well as the individual. [163],

Hulking imagery is a system of such perceptions of an individual that, through them, the concept of personality "spirituality" will understand all the phenomena and objects around them and form a certain attitude towards them. Even because they are social, they involve almost all areas of "spirituality": connecting oneself with the fate of the motherland, being able to be proud

of the history of their homeland, science, religion, religious and national values, traditions, visions of human-created hulking masterpieces.

Adolescent age one of the most important advantages of an individual is his knowledge of the external environment, adaptation to it in various situations, and the ability to bring up adequately acceptable norms of behavior. Because a person must know and appreciate the social and cultural achievements of society, be able to make them mentally and mentally ill. This thing gives him the opportunity to correctly perceive and understand his own time, making the world of the imagination of the personality of a teenage student flexible and submissive. From this, it is logical that our hulking visions are significant in that they play the role of a supposedly guiding and adapting criterion for behavior, behavior that clearly captures the personality of the reader in specific situations, in relation to values in society. Important norms of the teenage friendship code are honor, equality, loyalty, help to a friend, honesty.

Friendship norms possession is an important achievement of a child in adolescence. If he cannot find such a friend among his relatives and educators, then he will surely find a person who will support his interests and aspirations, and what will fill the shortcomings in him, among foreign adults or his peers. [332],

Hulking imagery is a branch of social imagination, and it is not certain cognitive objects that are hardened, but they are in constant development, movement and progress. Its initial stage is the stage of perception, in which the perception of information reflected directly in the mind occurs, which they sort from the point of view of awareness and necessity for the individual. This is followed by the second stage – the stage of associative connections, which means that new messages in the mind are compared with the old ones, and associative and hulking connections are taught. A common feature of the second step above is generalization– generalization. The next stages are more relevant to the field of thinking and concepts, in which each information or message is differentiated in terms of relevance to individ in a differential and, on this basis, determines the direction of personality behavior in the form of certain Masters.

Regarding the refinement of social perceptions, it should be said that in our opinion, the method of return plays an important role in this process. But what is being perceived over and over again should be of both xissial and intellectual importance to that listener. Returns, which have acquired a certain personal meaning and content, can lead to the consolidation of visions at the level of beliefs. In this regard, it should be taken into account that if the information arriving at the perception of an individual corresponds to his previously subjective imagination, it is recognized as correctly objectively Real, but takes place from the system of representations, if ustanovka is the opposite, and the information given may not perceive them as "false" if it does not correspond to the views of

Especially in adolescent age students, the reconstruction of imaginations and the change of views is much easier. In our Uzbek psychology, too, in addition to subordination to national values, there is no tendency to follow the opinion of authoritarian individuals and groups, to accept them without criticism.

The most puzzling of the problems faced by the individual in Phylogenesis, in the development of mankind, is human nature, inherent in its essence, despite the fact that a lot of research has been carried out in this regard, various theories have been stated, so far a clear, clear and concise answer has not been obtained. This is because the difference between humans is very diverse. These differences are prominent not only in appearance, but also in unpredictable and

complex behavior and temperament. Just as the more than seven billion people in the land Kurra are not exactly alike in appearance, so will the character, psychological characteristics. Such cases do not necessarily allow all representatives of mankind to be united on the basis of a certain classification.

Today, this issue is considered extremely relevant, zero at the same time, among the most important problems facing humanity can include rapid population growth, rising temperatures, environmental pollution, nuclear waste, drugs, alcoholism, racial discrimination, poverty, various destructive groups, the activities of currents and terrorism. All these problems arose as a result of the activities of people. In the future, what not only human tobacco will be like, but also our lives, remains to the effect of our aspirations on the way to understanding ourselves and each other. The biological existence of a person with the ability to consciousness, speech, work is no secret, but on the other hand he is also a social creature with the need to communicate and deal with others. Only when a person sees a person in the person of other people does he realize himself as a person, imagine.

Thus, destructive activity is susceptible to people who cannot meet their basic needs, E.As Fromm points out, they represent their "I" through demolition, destruction. It is an attempt to prove that destructiveness is relevant, first in its own eyes, then in the eyes of others, in a context in which it is extremely difficult to admit that it has no balance, prestige, attention.

Psychologically, the motivations of teenage students towards any (destructive or constructive) activity include the needs of his safety, respect, recognition and, finally, realization of his creative potential, self-expression.

Studies by the Institute for child and adolescent hygiene in recent years have found the importance of acute periods of ontogenesis in cases of increased neurotic and pathocharacterological types of neuromuscular deviations, which have acquired involuntary stubbornness, motile excitability, fear, pathological habits. Deviations like this were found in a number of children 3-4 years old, and with the passage of a sharp period, the amount of these disorders decreased, while at the age of 5-6 years of these children, that is, at the border of the transition to the next acute stage of ontogenesis, this deviation again increased significantly (Shashkova I.A.). In the tense period following these, higher results were obtained when children were examined in the first year of schooling. Pre-clinical level neuromuscular deviations have also been observed in most first graders. In connection with this, the question arises of how these diseases can be explained: whether they are in the quality of adaptation (adaptation) phenomena associated with changes in the social condition of children's access to school, or are mainly as a result of endogenous neurogumoral (hormonal) changes with a biological essence of the crisis period. Although a significant decrease in signs of illness with the passage of a tense period testifies to the importance of biological factors, it is also necessary to take into account the importance of social conditions in the non-adaptation of first graders to school. Information about the prevalence of one or another manifestations of neuromuscular diseases among children and adolescents can be given by repeated and closed studies on significant norms.

Children and adolescents' neuromuscular health studies are significant because this period is the basis of the health of the maturation period, and because this relatively non-large period of ontogenesis includes a number of sharp stages - such as the puberty (sexual maturity) period, the most complex period for the teenager himself and his entourage.

When the neuromuscular health of 12-year-old adolescents was examined, it was found that parts of the children also had deviations of an asthenoneurotic nature. While children suffer from sleep disorders, extreme fatigue, headaches, poor appetite, decreased ability to work, and some-from antibiotic or traffic intolerance, dizziness, fainting (vegetative-vascular diseases), others experience mainly neurotic phenomena: various brain-stuck habits, a tendency to fear, night enuresis, moonshine, nausea, tenderness, crying, etc. If one or another deviations were detected in 12 - year-old children, that is, in the first phase of the pubertal period, the frequency of diseases in adolescents of the second phase-14-15 years old-turned out to be high, and these diseases were also observed in students of the 8th grade. These adolescents had reduced the amount of asthenoneurotic events at the age of 16 and only showed up in isolation.

Thus, the result of these studies shows the importance of psychophysiological pubertal perturbations in the occurrence of complaints of adolescents with an asthenoneurotic nature. At the same time, anamnestic (on the history of the disease) data analysis allows us to talk about negative biological factors in the occurrence of various deviations in adolescent neuromuscular health, such as pregnancy, obstetric pathology, physical depletion. When comparing adolescent and pediatric anemnesis data with healthy children and adolescents with neuromuscular health deviations, the differences between them are many micro social conditions (parental literacy rate, Family Budget, home conditions, etc.) followed. Especially in domestic family relationships (character traits of family members, domestic alcoholism and cases of conflict and divorce associated with chronic alcoholism) it turns out that these differences are much greater. The results of the examination testify to the multifactorial nature of the neuromuscular health of children and adolescents and make it possible to distinguish between somatogenic, psychogenic and sociogenic etiology (origin)in the occurrence of its disorders.

It is associated with the need to determine the self-determination of a teenager and determine his purpose in life. This deprivation of aspirations and needs can create a crisis that is seen within the framework of the norm in the psychology of age periods, and in some cases, psychological behavioral manifestations in the field of psychiatry. Thus, the adolescence we are seeing is characterized by the highest imbalance, expressed in the degree of physical and psychological progress and in the pace by the contradictions that give rise to anomalous behavioral manifestations in social relations, and this responsible period is worthy of great attention from a psychologist, sociologist and doctors-psychiatrists and psychogogenists. If, in such a tense period, a teenager is not helped by reason, femininity in "finding identity", awareness of new interests, the most correct ways to establish normal relationships with adults are not found, then an undesirable behavior and behavioral reaction that deviates from the "norm of adolescence"may arise.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that in the formation of destructive behavior, aspects inherent in adolescence are of particular importance and, of course, differences from one another are observed.

The prosperous life of Tomorrow is determined by building society on the principles of perfect morality, the upbringing of a harmonious child in the family, by the fact that he becomes physically strong, spiritually trigger, spiritually mature, mentally and morally beautiful.

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